

lower value of B (816 cm^{-1}) indicates considerable covalent nature of the metal–ligand bond¹⁸. The lowering of ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.59) from 1.8 shows high-spin octahedral configuration for the complex. The value of covalency parameter (β) was found to be 0.78.

The electronic spectra of Co^{II} complex exhibited bands at 8 700, 17 500 and 21 540 cm^{-1} attributable to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, respectively. The ligand field parameters like B (818 cm^{-1}), $10 Dq$ ($9\,020 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), ν_2/ν_1 (0.02), β_{8g} (0.84) and (19.04) along with higher μ_{eff} value (Table 1) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry.

The Co^{II} complex showed one broad band at (13 900–15 800 cm^{-1}) (185 cm^{-1}) which can be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition which is a characteristic of distorted octahedral configuration¹⁹.

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Complexes of 4-Amino-3-mercapto-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-triazole with Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc- and Cadmium-(II) Ions

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IN the present paper we report the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-1,2,4-triazole (AMOPTH₂) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} .

Experimental

AMOPTH₂ was prepared as reported¹.

Preparation of metal complexes: Aqueous ethanolic solutions of metal(II) halide (0.005 mol in 60 ml) and the ligand (0.01 mol in 100 ml) were mixed in hot. pH of the mixed solution was raised slowly to 7–8 by adding concentrated ammonia and refluxed for 0.5 h. The Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes separated immediately but the Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes separated on adding equal volume of water. The product was filtered, washed with aqueous ethanol and dried at 90–100° (Table 1).

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis %: Found (Calcd.)		μ_{eff}^* B.M.
		M	N	
$\text{Co}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	Brown	19.65 (19.58)	18.61 (18.60)	4.82
$\text{Ni}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$	Bluish green	19.63 (19.52)	18.54 (18.62)	3.22
$\text{Cu}(\text{AMOPT})$	Brown	23.62 (23.57)	20.66 (20.77)	1.51
$\text{Zn}(\text{AMOPT})$	White	24.32 (24.09)	20.59 (20.63)	Diamag.
$\text{Cd}(\text{AMOPT})$	White	35.43 (35.30)	17.51 (17.58)	Diamag.

*At 304 K.

Ir, uv and visible reflectance spectra, and magnetic susceptibilities were determined as usual. For calculating effective magnetic moment values, correction was made for TIP contribution².

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analyses (Table 1) indicate that AMOPTH₂ forms 1 : 1 (metal–ligand) complexes with bivalent metal ions. The complexes, in general, are slightly soluble in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol and acetone but are insoluble in water. The methanol solutions of the com-

plexes are almost nonconducting ($\Lambda_{\infty} = 6-10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$) indicating their non-ionic character.

The room temperature magnetic moment values of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes (~ 4.82 and 3.22 B.M., respectively) indicate octahedral environment of ligand molecules around spin-free Co^{II} and Ni^{II} atoms². The Cu^{II} complex displays subnormal magnetic moment value (1.51 B.M.) attributed either to copper-copper bonding or super-exchange interaction³ through sulphur atom in complex molecules. Therefore the complex is probably dimeric or polymeric.

The solid reflectance spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{AMOPT})$ display a broad asymmetric band in the region $11\,760-14\,280 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a strong band at $23\,890 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to the combination of ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g} + {}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, respectively, in tetragonal field⁴. The reflectance spectra of $\text{Co}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ display a medium band near $17\,820-18\,520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a shoulder near $21\,340 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The former is assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) while the latter a consequence of spin-orbit coupling in ${}^4T_{1g}$ (P) state⁵. In ethanol, the complex, however, shows only one broad band at $18\,150 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 15$) in visible region attributed to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) of octahedral Co^{II} atom⁵. The reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{AMOPT})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ display a shoulder at $22\,730 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a broad medium band near $15\,870 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$ (P) transitions, respectively, in distorted octahedral field⁶. In solution, the complex displays these transitions as medium and broad bands at $16\,150$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 18$) and at $22\,950 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\epsilon_{\text{max}} 38$).

The disappearance of ν_{OH} and ν_{SH} ligand bands at $3\,110$ and $2\,752 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, in the ir spectra of the complexes suggests bonding of the ligand through deprotonated phenolic oxygen as well as thio sulphur. A broad band at $3\,050-3\,480 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in aquo complexes is attributed to ν_{OH} of water molecule. A strong band at $1\,592 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ligand is assigned to azomethine $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ which shifted to higher frequencies by $3-15 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in its complexes. The shift of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ at higher wave number in the complexes suggests the bonding of azomethine nitrogen with metal ions⁷. The ligand displays thioamide band-I at $1\,498 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which shifted to higher frequency near $1\,520-1\,537 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The thioamide band-II ($1\,278 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) also shifted to higher frequency in the complexes at $1\,280-1\,302 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The δ_{OH} of the ligand ($1\,350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) almost disappeared in the complexes indicating coordination of deprotonated phenolic oxygen. The ν_{CO} band of the ligand at $1\,260 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to higher wave numbers at $1\,290 \pm 12 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation⁸. The thioamide band-III ($1\,175 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) as expected moves to higher wave number^{9,9} by $5-25 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. The thioamide band-IV is observed at 903 cm^{-1} and it suffered a red-shift at $680 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The red-shift⁹ of thioamide band-IV supports the bonding through deprotonated thiol sulphur.

The Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes are in general tetrahedral. The ir spectra of the Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes consist of strong and well-resolved bands while those of the octahedral Ni^{II} , Co^{II} and tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes are ill-resolved. The difference may arise from the difference in structure of these complexes.

Analysis of ir spectral data reveals that the ligand coordinates through aldimine nitrogen (or amino nitrogen), deprotonation of OH proton, phenolic oxygen and mercapto sulphur in almost all the complexes. There is scope for bridging quadridentate mode of bonding by the ligand, leading to polynuclear species.

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Coordination Template Reactions. Part-IV. Synthesis of some Transition Metal Complexes derived from Dibenzo-(e,l)(2,3,9,10) tetraphenyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-1,3,8,10-tetraene- N_4

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METAL complexes of macrocyclic ligands have been known and some such derivatives have been prepared using phenylenediamine and related compounds¹⁻⁴. The present paper describes the template synthesis of some macrocyclic complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cr^{III} derived from